

of glaserite. One ton of glaserite produces 1.27 tons of K_2SO_4 . If glaserite is added to the remaining mother liquor, then another 0.6 t of K_2SO_4 can be obtained.

Figure 2. Phase diagram of the KCl-NaCl- K_2SO_4 - Na_2SO_4 system at 75°C

Thus, efficient, waste-free production of potassium sulfate can be organized in Turkmenistan.

REFERENCES

- [1]. M. M. Viktorov, Graphic calculations in the technology of inorganic substances. L.: Chemistry, pp. 464, 1972